

Angelo Leogrande^{1*o^}

*LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

°LUM Enterprise s.r.l., Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italy, EU

^University of Bari Aldo Moro

Spending on Innovation Other than Research and Development in Italian Regions

Increased on average by 21.44% between 2018 and 2023

The European Innovation Scoreboard calculates spending on innovation other than research and development. The variable is calculated as the total innovation expenditure of enterprises, excluding intramural and extramural R&D expenditures (Eurostat). This indicator measures spending on innovation unrelated to R&D as a percentage of total turnover. Many components of innovation expenditure, such as investments in equipment and machinery and the acquisition of patents and licenses, measure the diffusion of new technologies and production ideas. The data refer to the Italian regions between 2018 and 2023.

Analysis of Spending on Innovation Other than Research and Development in Italian Regions in 2023.

The analysis of data related to innovation expenditures, other than research and development, in Italian regions for the year 2023 reveals a varied landscape, with an average expenditure of about 121.64 per region. The region that stands out for having invested the most in innovation is Friuli Venezia Giulia, with an expenditure of 193.47, while Sardinia shows the lowest investment, with only 62.26. These data highlight a significant regional disparity in investment in innovation outside of research and development, suggesting that some regions, such as Friuli Venezia Giulia and Marche (with a notable investment of 170.02), place particular emphasis on innovation as a lever for growth and competitiveness. Conversely, regions like Sardinia and Valle d'Aosta (67.24) show significantly lower investments, perhaps reflecting differences in regional economic priorities or investment capacities. It is interesting to note that traditionally strong industrial and economic regions, such as Lombardy and Veneto, show innovation expenditures above the average, though not at the top. This may suggest a diversification of investment strategies in innovation, possibly more balanced between research and development and other forms of innovation.

Analysis of Spending on Innovation Other than Research and Development in Italian Regions Between 2018 and 2023. Analyzing the data related to innovation expenditures, other than research and development, in Italian regions between 2018 and 2023, a variety of regional dynamics can be observed. The average percentage change in these expenditures is 21.48%, while the average absolute

¹Assistant Professor of Economics at LUM University Giuseppe Degennaro and Researcher at LUM Enterprise s.r.l. Email: leogrande.culture@lum.it, Strada Statale 100 km 18, Casamassima, Bari, Puglia, Italia.

change is 21.66. This indicates a general increase in investment in innovation outside of research and development on a national scale. In particular, the region of Friuli Venezia Giulia shows the most significant increase in percentage terms, with a surprising 77.05%, perhaps reflecting an intense focus on new areas of innovation. Marche and Umbria also show notable increases, of 51.07% and 43.89% respectively, suggesting a strengthening of the commitment to innovation in these regions. On the contrary, Calabria and Liguria record a reduction in expenditures, of -31.84% and -8.59% respectively, indicating a possible contraction in investments in innovative initiatives or a reallocation of resources to other sectors. These data reflect the diversity of regional strategies in Italy in terms of investment in innovation, highlighting the importance of targeted policies that take into account local specificities. While some regions are decisively advancing towards innovation, others seem to be slowing down, emphasizing the need for a more coordinated national approach to maximize the country's innovative potential.

Italian Macro-Regions. The analysis of trends in innovation spending, excluding investments in research and development, in the Italian macro-regions from 2018 to 2023 provides an enlightening snapshot of the different areas of the country's approach to innovation. During this period, the South led the ranking in terms of total expenditure, accumulating an impressive figure of 755.37, highlighting a significant commitment to innovation. Despite this high expenditure, the region experienced notable fluctuations, culminating in a marked decrease in 2023 that brought its annual expenditure well below the previous trend. The North and Center, although having spent less overall than the South with 668.67 and 670.16 respectively, showed more stable and progressive spending patterns. In particular, the Center recorded steady growth, especially in the biennium 2021-2023, suggesting a sustained increase in interest and investments in innovative initiatives. This growth paralleled that of the North, which saw a slight decline in 2022 but promptly recovered in 2023, indicating resilience and continued commitment to innovation. Looking at average annual spending, the South again stands out with an average expenditure of about 125.89, higher than that of the North and Center, which spent on average about 111.44 and 111.69 respectively. This demonstrates that, despite the fluctuations, the South has overall invested more in innovative initiatives during the considered period. The overall average of 116.34 per year per macro-region underscores significant investment in innovation outside of traditional research and development. However, the year-on-year growth rates offer a more nuanced narrative, with the South showing greater volatility compared to the North and Center, which have shown more linear and sustained growth. This analysis highlights not only the importance of investments in innovation for regional growth and competitiveness but also how these expenditures are distributed and evolve over time. The significant variation in the South in 2023 could reflect specific challenges or a reallocation of priorities, while the steady growth in the North and Center suggests a more uniform and progressive approach to innovation. It is crucial for policymakers to observe these trends to guide future investment strategies, ensuring that innovation is at the heart of Italian economic development across all its macro-regions.

North-South Divide. The data analyzed on spending on innovation other than research and development in the Italian macro-regions from 2018 to 2023 provide a basis for discussing the existence of a North-South divide in terms of innovation investments. The main distinction emerges not so much from the total amount of expenditure—since the South has shown significant financial commitment, at times surpassing the other macro-regions—but rather from the growth trends and the volatility of investments over time. The South has recorded high expenditure, with significant peaks,

but has also shown greater volatility, culminating in a notable decrease in 2023. This fluctuation pattern could indicate less stability in innovation investments, which can be influenced by various factors such as changes in regional policies, availability of funding, or specific economic dynamics of the region. The marked reduction in investments in 2023 could signal a fragility in the commitment to innovation or a response to specific economic challenges that might accentuate the existing divide. On the contrary, the North and Center have demonstrated a more consistent and progressive approach to innovation investments. Although the North experienced a slight decline in 2022, it quickly recovered in 2023, highlighting resilience and sustained commitment. The Center, in particular, showed steady growth, especially in the recent years analyzed, suggesting greater stability and perhaps a more targeted strategy towards innovation. These trends indicate that, although the total expenditure may not differ drastically, the stability and continuity of innovation investments differ between the North and the South. This difference can contribute to a gap in terms of innovation outcomes and economic growth between the macro-regions, with the North and Center potentially being able to better and more sustainably leverage their innovation investments. In conclusion, the data support the argument for the existence of a North-South divide in terms of innovation investments, not so much in terms of total expenditure but rather concerning the consistency and stability of investments. To address and potentially reduce this divide, it would be crucial for the South to adopt strategies that ensure not only financial commitment to innovation but also the stability and sustainability of such investments in the long term.

Economic Policies to Increase Spending on Innovation Other Than Research and Development. In Italy, increasing spending on innovation, beyond traditional policies focused on research and development (R&D), requires a heterogeneous approach that takes into account the peculiarities of the different macro-regions. Among the most effective strategies are tax incentives and subsidized financing, such as tax credits for the adoption of advanced technologies and loans on favorable terms for SMEs and startups engaged in innovative processes. It is also essential to invest in training and skill development through targeted programs and collaborations between the private sector and academic institutions to ensure a highly qualified workforce. At the same time, the development of digital infrastructure, such as broadband and 5G, and the promotion of open innovation platforms are crucial steps to facilitate technological innovation. To support the internationalization of businesses and encourage collaboration, it is essential to offer assistance and incentives for exploring new markets, as well as promoting the creation of business networks and clusters that facilitate the exchange of knowledge and resources. Policies should also focus on reviewing regulations to remove obstacles to innovation and concentrate on key sectors for the regional economy, promoting the adoption of new technologies and processes. Attention to sustainable development and social innovation, through incentives for eco-sustainable solutions and support for projects that address social challenges, can significantly contribute to economic growth and technological progress. Implementing these policies requires coordinated action among governments, businesses, academia, and civil society to create an innovative ecosystem that stimulates competitiveness and sustainability in the different Italian macro-regions. This integrated approach, aiming to enhance regional specificities and promote inclusive and accessible innovation, can accelerate the path towards a more prosperous and technologically advanced future.

Differences Between Innovation and Research and Development. Research and development (R&D) and technological innovation are closely related but distinct concepts, both essential for progress and

competitiveness in the modern world. Research and development represent the process through which new knowledge is discovered and applied to develop new products, services, or processes, or to improve existing ones. This process is often divided into basic research, which focuses on acquiring new knowledge without an immediate application goal, and applied research, which aims to solve specific problems. Development, on the other hand, refers to the use of knowledge acquired from research to create new products or processes or to improve existing ones. Technological innovation, however, extends beyond the realm of R&D to include the implementation of technologically advanced products, processes, or services. It is not limited to the creation of new technologies but also includes the adoption, adaptation, and use of existing technologies in new or improved ways. Technological innovation can stem from R&D but can also emerge from practical ingenuity, market experience, or internal organizational changes that allow for more effective use of technologies. While R&D is often concentrated on advancing knowledge and creating technological potential, technological innovation is the engine that transforms these potentials into tangible results that can be marketed or used to improve efficiency and quality of life. In this sense, R&D can be seen as an investment in the innovation potential of an organization or society, while technological innovation represents the realization of this potential in the form of products, processes, and services that add value to the economy and society.

Conclusions. The value of spending on innovation has grown on average in Italian regions by an amount equal to 21.44% between 2018 and 2023, increasing from an amount of 100.16 units to a value of 121.63 units. The region that spent the most in terms of innovation in 2023 is Friuli Venezia Giulia, with a value of 193.47 units, followed by Marche with 170.02 units and Umbria with 157.13 units. Sardinia is the last region for spending on innovation other than research and development in 2023, with a value of 62.26 units. Central Italy is the macro-region with the highest spending on technological innovation, with a value of 139.02 units in 2023, followed by the North with 127.20 and the South with 107.39. Central Italy is also the macro-region that had the most significant growth both in absolute terms between 2018 and 2023 with a value of 37.13% and in percentage terms with +36.45%.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

References

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A.(2020). The innovation-employment nexus in Europe. American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR), 4(11), 166-187.

Leogrande, A., Saponaro, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). A GIS based estimation of quality of life in Italian regions. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)* e-ISSN.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, A. (2021). The intellectual assets in Europe. Available at SSRN 3956755.

Magazzino, C., & Leogrande, A. (2020). Subjective well-being in Italian regions: A panel data approach.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The attractiveness of European research systems. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(10), 72-101.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Research and Development Expenditures on ESG Model in the Global Economy. Available at SSRN 4414232.

Leogrande, A. (2023). The Rule of Law in the ESG Framework in the World Economy. Available at SSRN 4355016.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The impact of R&D investments on corporate performance in European Countries. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(7), 186-201.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Political Stability in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4406997.

Leogrande, A., Laureti, L., & Costantiello, A. (2022). The Innovation Index in Europe. Available at SSRN 4091597.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Enterprises Providing ICT Training in Europe. Available at SSRN 4021150.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Labor Force Participation Rate in the Context of ESG Models at World Level. Available at SSRN 4466452.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Impact of Voice and Accountability in the ESG Framework in a Global Perspective. Available at SSRN 4398483.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Role of Government Effectiveness in the Light of ESG Data at Global Level. Available at SSRN 4324938.

Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., Leogrande, A., & Matarrese, M. (2021). The Innovation Linkages in Europe. Available at SSRN 3983218.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Satisfaction with the Environmental Condition in the Italian Regions between 2004 and 2020. Available at SSRN 4061708.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). Foreign Doctorate Students in Europe. Available at SSRN 4032975.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Matarrese, M., & Leogrande, A. (2022). The Employment in Innovative Enterprises in Europe. Available at SSRN 4010098.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, D. (2021). The Determinants of Landscape and Cultural Heritage Among Italian Regions in the Period 2004-2019. Available at SSRN 3971174.

Leogrande, A., Massaro, A., & Galiano, A. M. (2020). The Determinants of Innovation in European Countries in the period 2010-2019. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 4(8), 91-126.

Ferri, G., & Leogrande, A. (2015). Was the Crisis due to a shift from stakeholder to shareholder finance? Surveying the debate.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., Massaro, A., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The Role of Renewable Energy Consumption in Promoting Sustainability and Circular Economy: A Data-Driven Analysis. In *Data-Driven Intelligent Business Sustainability* (pp. 360-386). IGI Global.

Leogrande, A., & Costantiello, A. (2023). The Role of GDP Growth in the ESG Approach at World Level. Available at SSRN 4434206.

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2023). The Regulatory Quality and ESG Model at World Level. Available at SSRN 4388957.

Leogrande, A., Magaletti, N., Cosoli, G., & Massaro, A. (2022). Fixed Broadband Take-Up in Europe. Available at SSRN 4034298.

Leogrande, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrande, D. (2021). The Determinants of Design Applications in Europe. Available at SSRN 3956853.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2021). THE DETERMINANTS OF FIRM INVESTMENTS IN RESEARCH AND DEVELOPMENT. In *IAI ACADEMIC CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS Education and Social Sciences Business and Economics* (pp. 55-67).

Costantiello, A., & Leogrande, A. (2024). The regulatory quality in the light of environmental, social and governance framework at world level. *Discover Global Society*, 2(1), 1-20.

Magazzino, C., Madaleno, M., Waqas, M., & Leogrande, A. (2024). Exploring the determinants of methane emissions from a worldwide perspective using panel data and machine learning analyses. *Environmental Pollution*, 348, 123807.

Appendix

